

PHYTOCHEMICAL ANALYSIS OF DRIED EXTRACT OBTAINED FROM PLANTS USED IN BILIARY TRACT AND LIVER DISEASES

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Relevance: Currently, liver and gallbladder diseases are widespread among the population, often resulting from irregular eating habits, excessive consumption of fatty products, physical inactivity, and the stagnation of bile. While synthetic strong medications are effective, they also have side effects. Medicinal plants are free from such drawbacks and are a source for obtaining new drugs. It is crucial to develop the use of these plants in medical practice and create effective phytopreparations for treatment, as well as to prevent liver and biliary tract diseases.

Objective of the research: To obtain and standardize a dry extract from medicinal plants used in the biliary tract and liver diseases.

Methods and materials: The biologically active supplement used for bile secretion consists of the following medicinal plants: flowers of the baldrian plant, above-ground part of garden cornflower, fruits of wild carrot, roots of turmeric, corn silk, millet, pepper mint leaves, and the above-ground part of marshmallow plant. The extract was obtained through percolation with 70% ethanol. The extracts were evaluated based on their external appearance, odor, taste, color, dry residue, alcohol strength or density, heavy metals, and active substances after purification from impurities. The resulting liquid extract was filtered and concentrated in a water bath. The amount of dry residue in the liquid extract was determined using the method described in XI DF (Pharmacopeia). In the subsequent analysis of the raw materials, a gravimetric method for determining polysaccharides was developed, which involved precipitation and the collection of polysaccharides.

The flavonoids in the obtained liquid extract were identified using spectrophotometric methods, while coumarins were identified using chromatographic spectrophotometric methods. The content of the active substances in the medicinal products was determined using the Levental-Kursanov method, accepted in XI DF. This method is based on the oxidation of the analytes in acidic conditions with potassium permanganate.

Results: The extraction efficiency for flavonoids was found to be 1.98%, while for dry substances it was 9.31%. It was shown that double extraction ensured an average of 85-90% separation of bioactive compounds from the raw materials. The presence of flavones, flavanones, and flavonols was confirmed chromatographically. Upon percolation (extraction) with 20%, 40%, 70%, and 90% ethanol, the total flavonoid content was determined to be 2.1%, 4.1%, 6.9%, and 4.1% respectively. Quantitative analysis of flavonoids was performed using a photocolometric method. The analysis of polysaccharide content revealed a range from 9.63% to 10.98%. Based on this information, a moderate indicator of polysaccharide content was established, not lower than 9%. The amount of active substances determined by spectrophotometry was found to be 2.03%, while according to permanganatometry, it was $2.56 \pm 0.21\%$. The permanganatometry method was observed to be the most suitable for determining the amount of active substances and for standardization according to XI DF.

Conclusions: Based on the medicinal plants grown and found in the wild in our Republic, a dry extract intended for the treatment of biliary tract and liver diseases was obtained. The physical-

chemical properties of the medicinal raw materials (BASs) were studied based on the methods specified in the standards, and a phytochemical analysis was carried out. The main active compounds of the dry extract—flavonoids, polysaccharides, and active substances—were determined both qualitatively and quantitatively. It was recorded that with an increase in the concentration of alcohol during the extraction of the BASs, the amounts of extractive substances and flavonoids also increased.